

little as 10 mg. can be determined by this method. Common anions like chloride, bromide, nitrate, etc. do not interfere in the determination of the violet colour complexes [Y L Cu, Mg], [Y L Cu, Ca], [Y L Cu, Sr] and [Y L Cu, Ba] are still stable upto 250°, above this temperature they start decomposing. Only the MgCu complexes are soluble in methyl alcohol. The remaining are insoluble in water, acetone, alcohol, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, ether, benzene and pyridine.

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Spectrophotometric studies of Cu(II) complexes with Schiff Bases

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THE complexes of copper with sulphamethazine salicylaldimine (SUMTSA), sulphadiazinesalicylaldimine (SUDSA) and sulphamerazine salicylaldimine (SUMRSA) have been studied spectrophotometrically at 20°. Cu(II) forms 1:2 complexes with these ligands. Stability constants are determined by applying Job's method and Raghavrao's method. Free energy values have also been evaluated.

The synthesis and analysis of ligands have been described in previous communications^{1,2,3}.

A Beckman model Du spectrophotometer was used for absorption measurements. The studies were carried out in acetone/alcohol (1:1 by vol.) mixture.

The max. for copper acetate was found at 765nm., that of Cu-SUDSA complex at 330nm. (pH7.0) of Cu-SUMTSA complex at 395nm. (pH7.0) and of Cu-SUMRSA complex at 340nm (pH7.0). These wavelengths were chosen for the study of stoichiometry of the components by Job's method of continuous variation using equimolar solutions. The validity of Beer's law was seen. The absorbance measurements were carried out after 24 hr of equilibration. The colour did not fade even after a week. The pH of the solution were adjusted at required level by using different buffer solutions.

The stability constants were calculated from absorbance data (a) by extrapolation of Job's curve

obtained by using equimolar solutions as suggested by Raghavarao⁴, (b) using Job's method of nonequimolar solutions as modified by Foley-Anderson⁵ and Dey⁶.

The values of stability constants and free energy changes are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I. STABILITY CONSTANTS

S. No.	Complex	Method A		Method B	
		log K	$\frac{\Delta G}{K \text{ cal/mole}}$	log K	$\frac{\Delta G}{K \text{ cal/mole}}$
1	Cu-SUMTSA	9.08	-11.35	10.04	-12.55
2.	Cu-SUDSA	9.65	-12.06	10.52	-13.15
3.	Cu-SUMRSA	9.03	-11.29	10.40	-13.00

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The Effect of Bubble Formation on Hydrogen Overpotential at Mercury Cathodes

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BUBBLE overvoltages¹ were traditionally recorded to indicate the "minimum" overvoltage for electrolytic gas evolution reactions. Contemporary electrode kinetics² pays no heed to such subjective observations, which appear to have no fundamental significance. We wish to report a new effect, that of bubble formation on hydrogen overpotential measurements at high purity (5X distilled) mercury.

A centro-symmetric cell was used, with connecting tubes to the anode and reference hydrogen electrodes directly above the mercury cup. Hydrochloric acid

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NOTES

(0.1M), pre-electrolyzed at a mercury cathode at 10 mA cm^{-2} , further purified by passage through freshly activated charcoal³ upon entry to the cell, was used as electrolyte. Elhygen (electrolytic H_2 , diffused through Pd/Ag alloy) hydrogen was used to stir the catholyte, the reference and anode compartments being supplied with "prepurified" H_2 , purified through Deoxo and BTS catalysts and a liquid N_2 trap. To minimize ingress of air, Pyrex and copper gas supply lines were used throughout. Prolonged galvanostatic experiments (Metrohm polarograph) were made with stepwise changes of current at intervals of 1 to 100 hr.

In common with Post and Hiskey⁴, we find⁵ that the cathode potential drifts continuously more negative at an ever-diminishing rate as electrolysis proceeds. This behaviour contrasts with that of lead⁶ under similar conditions, the potential of which drifts positively during electrolysis. It is suggested, nevertheless, that the opposite potential drifts stem from a common origin—the gradual saturation of the metal with atomic hydrogen, which somehow influences the electronic properties of the metal. Cathodes of iron a metal well known to take up atomic hydrogen in electrolysis, also drift systematically to negative potentials⁷.

In the case of mercury, evidence directly connecting the hydrogen overpotential with hydrogen bubbles attached to the surface is illustrated by Fig. 1, which

Fig. 1.

shows the potential shift and recovery accompanying detachment of a single large bubble from the metal surface. Similar galvanostatic observations have been made for the current density range 0.02 to 0.6 mA cm^{-2} . The potential shift is generally larger, the larger is the bubble, in the range 1.0 to 4.0 mV . At 0.2 mA cm^{-2} , a periodic growth (period ca. 3h) and collapse of overpotential has been observed to coincide with the growth and detachment of bubbles.

Attempts⁸ to explain the observations in terms of the shielding effect of a bubble on the effective electrode area are not successful in accounting for the details of Fig. 1, in particular the rapid partial recovery of potential which corresponds to the growth of only a *minute* bubble. It is interesting to note that the growing bubble does not appear to result from the coalescence of numerous smaller bubbles, as is found to occur at higher current densities where the effects described are no longer of significance.

A reasonable explanation of the observations is that the overpotential is linked to the hydrogen content and/or surface coverage, θ_H , of the metal, both of which are thought to increase gradually during prolonged constant current electrolysis. Loss of a hydrogen bubble is then accompanied by a decrease in θ_H , which, however, recovers relatively rapidly by out-diffusion from the bulk metal. Observations confirm the relative constancy⁵ of overpotentials found for a particular current density after sufficient time ($\sim$ tens of hours) has elapsed to build up a stationary hydrogen concentration in the metal. Upon stepwise change of current density, particularly downwards, the instantaneous and steady-state overpotentials were markedly different, presumably because of the requirement to re-establish an "equilibrium" concentration of hydrogen in the metal (such a concentration being a function of the hydrogen atom flux arising from the electrolysis). Support for these ideas comes from the result⁹ that the volumes of hydrogen gas collected above a mercury cathode in hydrochloric acid over the same current density range are significantly lower than those anticipated from the product of charge passed and time of electrolysis, according to Faraday's Law.

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